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To cite this article: Konstantinos Louzis *et al* 2025 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **3123** 012030

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A Systems-Theoretic approach to assessing the safety of autonomous inland waterway vessels: Towards the development of the SeaGuard tool

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Abstract. The increasing integration of automation in inland waterway transport introduces safety risks due to complex control dependencies and cyber-physical vulnerabilities. Traditional risk assessment methodologies are limited in addressing such systemic hazards, particularly in the context of autonomous operations. This study applies the Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) to evaluate the safety of a conceptual autonomous inland vessel developed under the Horizon Europe AUTOFLEX project. The analysis identifies Unsafe Control Actions (UCAs), causal scenarios, and safety constraints, while also integrating cybersecurity considerations through the STPA-SafeSec framework. The results inform the design of the SeaGuard tool—a real-time anomaly detection and safety monitoring module. The paper demonstrates a structured, integrated methodology for enhancing safety and cyber-resilience in next-generation autonomous inland waterway systems.

1. Introduction

Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) is evolving through increased integration of automation and autonomy, offering gains in operational efficiency and navigational precision (1). However, these advances introduce systemic safety challenges, due to software-driven control, reduced human oversight, and cyber-physical dependencies, as shown, e.g., by Spachtholz et al. that increasing levels of autonomy introduce several new hazards compared to conventional inland vessels (2).

Autonomous inland vessels are increasingly conceptualized as highly interconnected Cyber-Physical Systems, CPS, (1), where system behaviour emerges not only from hardware and sensors, but also from control software, communication networks, and real-time decision-making processes. Furthermore, the absence of onboard crew places greater reliance on feedback accuracy, real-time coordination, and system integrity. This shifts the focus of hazard identification beyond mechanical failure into unsafe interactions, degraded control loops, and timing mismatches. Such phenomena cannot be captured by methods originating from the reliability domain, such as Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) due to the underlying linear causality logic, which translates to an inability to model

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software faults or system-wide emergent behaviour inherent in autonomous systems (3). Furthermore, other hazard identification methods, such as Preliminary Hazard Analysis (PHA) often lack a structured approach and fail to capture interdependencies, or cybersecurity threats (4). Other methodological challenges relate to the dependence on past failure data for quantifying risk, which are not available for systems such as autonomous ships. These constraints are especially problematic in early design phases, where information about system architecture is limited. Another challenge that relates to increasing levels of autonomy and CPSs in general is that cybersecurity becomes a critical dimension of safety analysis (5). Software-driven vessels are vulnerable to cyber incidents that may disrupt control logic or feedback signals (6). For autonomous vessels, these challenges require risk assessment approaches that account for local operational constraints and system-level interactions between physical and cyber components (see 7).

To overcome these limitations, systemic approaches such as the Systems-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) focus on safety as an emerging property from the system's control structure rather than focusing on the failures of individual system components (8). STPA identifies Unsafe Control Actions (UCAs), their causal paths, and safety constraints necessary to prevent losses. In addition, STPA can effectively address both software failures and cyber-security issues (9) and some extensions to the base methodology have been proposed to address the relationship between cyber-security and safety. For example, the STPA-SafeSec extension captures integrity and availability threats by linking cyber-attacks to safety outcomes (10).

To ensure safe autonomous operation for vessels navigating in Inland Waterways (IWW), the Horizon Europe AUTOFLEX project designs such a vessel for confined waterways at the conceptual level that will be equipped with the SeaGuard supervisory controller, which is being developed within the project and aims to serve the specific needs of autonomous inland waterway navigation. SeaGuard is intended to be an online tool that detects anomalies in terms of deviations from the safe system state (e.g. due to limited manoeuvring space and proximity to infrastructure), assesses the magnitude of the deviation in terms of the risk of compromising vessel capabilities, and suggests feasible measures for controlling risk; see (11) for a description of its functionalities. The main objective of this paper is to determine requirements for the behaviour of SeaGuard with respect to maintaining system safety and cybersecurity constraints. The methodology involves applying STPA with selected elements from STPA-SafeSec to the autonomous operation of the AUTOFLEX vessel, for identifying UCAs, constraints, and loss scenarios that include both random failures and cybersecurity-related causes that can cascade in safety-related losses. The results will be used to inform the development of the algorithms that will accomplish the functionalities of SeaGuard.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of related STPA applications in maritime systems. Section 3 outlines the methodology. Section 4 presents results related to the behaviour of SeaGuard for maintaining the safety of the vessel of interest. The paper concludes with a summary and outline of the next research steps.

2. Background

STPA adopts a system-level perspective, modelling control actions, feedback loops, and identifying constraints to uncover causes that can lead to unsafe system states and losses. In the autonomous ship domain, there have been several applications of STPA for ocean-going vessels, often combined with other methodologies such as Bayesian Networks (BN).

Wróbel et al. applied STPA to a generic architecture of remotely controlled merchant vessels that included the vessel, shore facilities, the organizational environment, as well as the operational environment (12). Given the control structure uncertainties related to the early stages of development of this technology, the authors identified that the following factors will be important for ensuring safe operation: the reliability of the vessel's systems, the availability of the communication between the vessel and shore-based facilities (e.g., for remote monitoring), as well as controls at the organizational and regulatory levels. Chaal et al. developed a framework for evaluating Risk Control Options (RCOs) in the design phase based on hazardous scenarios identified through STPA and a BN for quantifying the resulting risk level (13). The method was demonstrated in an autonomous seawater cooling system and the authors concluded that testing the software controller functionalities and integrating sensor health monitoring are expected to provide significant risk reduction for this system. Yang et al. adapted the conventional STPA to identify hazardous scenarios related to the transition between autonomy levels for autonomous marine systems with dynamic autonomy (i.e. that changes during operation) and considered the responsibility shifts between human and machine and how their process models need to be changed (14). Sumon et al. used STPA to determine the safest control mode (e.g., fully autonomous, operator-assisted etc.) for an autonomous ship depending on the operational phase (e.g., port approach, berthing etc.) by comparing the UCAs and loss scenarios identified for the control structures that reflect the different control modes (15).

The literature also includes some examples of inland-specific STPA applications. Zhang et al. applied the method to a remotely-controlled model of an inland vessel, which also includes an integrated risk assessment system, and evaluate the effectiveness of safety strategies in different autonomy levels (16). The authors conclude that the remote-control station, the communication between ship and shore, as well as the onboard virtual captain have the most significant effect on system safety and that having some crew onboard may reduce the overall risk, compared to fully autonomous operation.

The cascading effects of cyber-attacks to system safety have been addressed methodologically by extending STPA with specific guidance to identify such hazardous scenarios, such as the work by de Souza et al who combine STPA with a threat model to expand the scope of the identified loss scenarios (17). STPA-SafeSec expands STPA by linking cybersecurity threats, such as spoofed sensor inputs or Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks, to safety-critical failures through the violation of cybersecurity constraints (10). The practical contributions include the definition of a component layer that is associated with the abstract control structure, and a causal factor taxonomy specific to the cybersecurity domain for integrity (e.g., command injection, measurement manipulation etc.) and availability (e.g., communication drop, node overload etc.) threats. Zhou et al. have developed the STPA-SynSS method to address the limitations of other frameworks, such as the STPA-SafeSec, and applied to an autonomous ship concept (6). The method adds the identification of functional requirements associated to safety and cybersecurity constraints to inform the control structure, a mapping between the control structure and system components to inform the loss scenarios. Gomola and Utne build on the STPA-SynSS to develop the STPA-SW-SAF-SEC approach, which extends the framework to consider the effect of software failures on system safety along the effect of intentional cyber-attacks (9). The authors use the Systems Modelling Language (SysML) for a more formal description of the system architecture and how it operates and use dynamic and static control structures, derived from corresponding system representations, to handle the complexity of software failures.

3. Methodology

This study applies the STPA to identify potential loss scenarios in autonomous inland waterway operations, combined with elements from STPA-SafeSec, to examine how cybersecurity threats can lead to safety-related outcomes in the context of loss scenarios that emerge from the violation of system-level safety and cybersecurity constraints. The analysis at the component level with hardware-level mappings proposed by STPA-SafeSec is not used since the system of interest is being designed at the conceptual and preliminary stage.

Our methodology applies the following four steps (see Figure 1), adapted from the STPA Handbook, to identify causal paths that may lead to system-level losses (8):

1. Identification of unacceptable losses, the system hazards that could lead to them, and the safety constraints required to prevent those hazards. For example, for the system-level hazard “the vessel enters a restricted area” the associated safety constraint can be expressed as “the vessel must avoid restricted areas”. In this step, cyber-security constraints are also identified, as proposed by STPA-SafeSec, which can be violated by attacks targeting availability (e.g. denial-of-service attacks etc.) and integrity (e.g. spoofing, logic tampering etc.).
2. Representation of the system as a hierarchy of controllers, actuators, and feedback mechanisms. Controllers issue commands based on sensor inputs and internal logic to achieve operational goals, while controlled processes respond and provide feedback.
3. Identification of UCAs, which are control actions that may lead to system-level hazards under worst-case environmental conditions and are categorized in the following four types: not provided when required; provided when inappropriate; issued too early, too late, or in the wrong sequence; applied for too long or terminated too soon.
4. Identification of Loss Scenarios, where the potential causes (e.g., degraded feedback, software bugs, or erroneous process models) that can lead to UCAs are examined. Loss scenarios can be traced to both physical faults (e.g., GNSS failure), which violate safety constraints, and cybersecurity-related triggers (e.g., spoofed sensor inputs), which violate cybersecurity constraints. For identifying potential cyber-attacks, we have used the taxonomy proposed by STPA-SafeSec.

Figure 1. Methodology for Safety and Cybersecurity Analysis.

4. Results

This section describes the results from the implementation of the methodology outlined in Chapter 3 to the conceptual autonomous inland waterway vessel developed within the context of the AUTOFLEX project.

The AUTOFLEX vessel is designed to carry containerized cargo autonomously (i.e. without crew onboard and remotely monitored) in confined inland waterways (see 18). In terms of propulsion, the vessel is fully electric, equipped with two azimuth thrusters, powered by containerized battery packs that include an integrated fire suppression system. For navigation, the vessel relies on software controllers that are provided with data fused from sensors, including AIS, Radar, LiDAR, and infrared cameras. The operational context considered for the analysis is navigation during transit and port approach.

4.1 Define the Purpose of the Analysis

This step identifies unacceptable losses in the AUTOFLEX operational context, the hazardous conditions that could lead to the losses, and the safety constraints required to prevent such hazards (see Figure 2).

The identified losses and associated system-level hazards have been based on the particularities affecting the safety of inland navigation, which include narrow-channel geometries (i.e. limited manoeuvring space), seasonal depth variations, proximity to infrastructure, such as bridges and locks, as well as high vessel traffic density that also includes recreational users (see 19). In this context, the analysis presented in this paper considers losses related to human life, the cargo, the vessel and infrastructure, and loss of vessel control. These losses have been associated with system-level hazards that relate to fire threatening the cargo and the structural integrity of the vessel, unsafe distance to other vessels and obstacles, navigation within restricted (i.e. “no-go”) areas, the power distribution among vessel subsystems, and unauthorized access to vessel control systems.

Figure 2. Mapping between losses (red), system-level hazards (orange), and safety constraints (green).

The system-level hazards have been associated with safety constraints that need to be maintained, as shown in Figure 2, as well as the following cybersecurity constraints, which protect the controllers’ internal logic against corrupted input (integrity requirement) and missing or untimely feedback (availability requirement):

- **CSTR-I-1:** The integrity of all input data must be validated prior to issuing control actions.
- **CSTR-A-1:** All input data must be available at the time required for issuing control actions.

4.2 Modelling the System’s Control Structure

The AUTOFLEX vessel can be considered as a cyber-physical system, which integrates multiple subsystems that interact through feedback loops. The main controllers and their responsibilities are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Identified controllers and their responsibilities in the control structure.

Controller	Responsibility	Required feedback
SeaControl	Issues navigation commands for path planning and collision avoidance	Fused sensor information from the situational awareness system SeaSight and current speed and heading from the AutoPilot
AutoPilot	Executes navigation commands provided by SeaControl	Speed and heading from the propulsion and manoeuvring system.
SeaGuard	Monitors system state and intervenes when anomalies are detected (e.g., adjusting power distribution, activating fire suppression, or stopping the vessel)	Information from all controllers regarding system status

Controller	Responsibility	Required feedback
Remote Operations Centre (ROC)	Provides remote monitoring and supervisory control if required	Information from all controllers regarding system status
Energy Management System (EMS)	Ensures continuous and sufficient power delivery	Information about power consumption onboard the vessel
Emergency Systems	Alarm system for detecting critical onboard conditions, e.g. fire detection	Information from temperature sensors

The control structure shown in Figure 3 provides the foundation for identifying UCAs in the following section.

Figure 3. Control Structure of the AUTOFLEX Vessel (solid lines indicate Control Actions, dashed lines indicate Feedback).

4.3 Identification of Unsafe Control Actions (UCAs)

In total, 36 UCAs were identified for all controllers that have been included in the control structure shown in Figure 3. Table 2 lists selected UCAs for the control actions SeaGuard is responsible for. Each UCA is associated with the hazard(s) it may lead to, based on the context and timing of the action.

Table 2. Unsafe Control Actions (UCAs) for SeaGuard.

Control Action	UCA Type	Description
1.1 Adjust power distribution	Provided when not required	Adjusts power when subsystems are already stable, destabilizing control functions [H1, H3, H4]
1.2 Activate suppression system	Not provided	Does not activate the fire suppression system upon fire detection, allowing it to spread [H2]
1.3 Activate suppression system	Applied too long/ stopped too soon	Disables the fire suppression system before the fire is fully resolved, allowing it to rekindle and spread [H2]
1.4 Override AutoPilot	Incorrect timing	Reduces speed too late when the vessel is on a collision course with an obstacle or another vessel without leaving enough time to avoid the collision [H3]
1.5 Override AutoPilot	Not provided	Does not stop the vessel when approaching a low-clearance bridge [H3]

The following constraints have been identified for SeaGuard to avoid executing control actions in an unsafe way:

- **C1:** SeaGuard must adjust power distribution to safety-critical subsystems immediately after verifying power is insufficient [UCA1.1].
- **C2:** SeaGuard must activate the fire suppression system immediately after a fire has been detected and the presence of fire has been verified [UCA1.2].
- **C3:** SeaGuard must disable the fire suppression system after verifying that the fire has been successfully extinguished [UCA1.3].
- **C4:** SeaGuard must reduce vessel speed after verifying that the vessel is on a collision course, has non-zero speed, and SeaControl is not fulfilling its responsibility of initiating collision avoidance manoeuvres, to a magnitude and at a time that mitigates the severity of the collision or increases the likelihood of avoiding it [UCA1.4].
- **C5:** SeaGuard must stop the vessel after verifying that the vessel is approaching a low-clearance bridge, and SeaControl is not fulfilling its responsibility of avoiding the collision with the bridge, at a time that mitigates the severity of the collision or increases the likelihood of avoiding it [UCA1.5].

4.4 Identification of Loss Scenarios

The causal factors that have been identified in the loss scenarios are related to the process model of SeaGuard, random faults, and cyber-attacks that violate the integrity and availability

requirement. The following scenarios are directly linked to the selected UCAs related to SeaGuard that were described in the previous section:

- **SG-LS1**-Power distribution false anomaly: The azimuth thrusters are provided with sufficient power during transit. SeaGuard adjusts power distribution unnecessarily [UCA 1.1], reducing power to the azimuth thrusters during a turning manoeuvre and therefore steering effectiveness, because it believes power is too much in this operational context. This will occur if SeaGuard has identified a false anomaly in the power distribution due to an incorrect internal process model (e.g. a misconfigured threshold).
- **SG-LS2**-Fire suppression not activated: A fire is detected onboard the vessel. SeaGuard does not activate the fire suppression system [UCA 1.2] because it believes there is no fire. This will occur if the fire detection system incorrectly reports that the temperature is normal. The indication will be incorrect if any of the following occur: temperature sensor fault or a spoofing cyber-attack that manipulates temperature readings to falsely indicate normal values, both of which violate the integrity requirement, or an incorrect temperature threshold in SeaGuard's internal process model.
- **SG-LS3**-Fire suppression prematurely stopped: A fire is detected onboard the vessel and SeaGuard activates the fire suppression system on time. SeaGuard deactivates the suppression system prematurely [UCA 1.3] because it believes the fire has been extinguished. This will occur if temperature feedback is inaccurate due to a sensor fault or spoofing cyber-attack (integrity violation), or if updated readings are missing because of delayed or lost communication (availability violation).
- **SG-LS4**-Collision with obstacle/vessel not avoided: An obstacle or vessel has been detected that needs to be avoided, but SeaControl fails to initiate collision avoidance manoeuvres. SeaGuard, acting as a fallback mechanism, reduces vessel speed to late to avoid the collision [UCA 1.4] because it believes the distance from the obstacle or vessel is greater than it actually is. This will occur if the distance provided by SeaSight is incorrect due to sensor faults or sensor spoofing (integrity violation) or not available on time due to network dropout or denial-of-service attack (availability violation).
- **SG-LS5**-Collision with low-clearance bridge not avoided: The vessel approaches a low-clearance bridge, but SeaControl fails to identify the presence of the bridge. SeaGuard, acting as a fallback mechanism, does not stop the vessel to avoid the collision [UCA1.5] because it incorrectly assesses the vertical clearance as sufficient for the vessel to navigate under the bridge. This will occur if sensor data is spoofed (integrity violation) or unavailable due to sensor faults or network dropout (availability violation).

5. Conclusions

In this paper, STPA was combined with the cybersecurity constraints concept and cyber-attack taxonomy from STPA-SafeSec to determine requirements for SeaGuard, which aims to detect deviations from the safe system state during operation due to the violation of safety and cybersecurity constraints. The methodology was applied to a preliminary architecture of the inland vessel designed at the conceptual level within the AUTOFLEX project.

The requirements for SeaGuard that resulted from the analysis state that it must verify the information used to determine the need for applying a control action, such as adjusting power distribution and activating the fire suppression system. SeaGuard must also ensure control actions are applied with appropriate timing to effectively control risk, as well as include mechanisms to handle false detections and errors in its process model. The integrity and availability requirements from STPA-SafeSec highlight the need to integrate cybersecurity into early-stage safety assessments given that their violation can trigger hazardous scenarios due to the dependencies between cyber vulnerabilities and safety-critical control actions.

The next steps of our research involve identifying process variables from STPA to determine the indicators that should be monitored for anomalies by the algorithms that will be included in SeaGuard. The analysis will also be iterated to determine a more complete set of requirements by increasing the level of abstraction of the functional and structural architecture of the AUTOFLEX vessel as it evolves. Adding more details will allow a more elaborate specification of how the subsystems interact, which will be reflected in updated versions of the control structure, and subsequently allow the identification of additional UCAs and loss scenarios. This will also allow elaborating on the cybersecurity aspect by including in the analysis the component diagram, as proposed by STPA-SafeSec. This will result in the identification of additional constraints on the behaviour of SeaGuard with respect to maintaining minimum risk conditions for the system. Finally, the performance of SeaGuard in terms of aspects including reliability and scalability will be validated in simulation-based experiments that will be conducted for representative real-world scenarios.

Acknowledgments

The paper presents the outcomes of research conducted within the framework of the project AUTOFLEX (AUTOnomous small and FLEXible vessels) which received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Programme under the Grant Agreement 101136257.

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